

Pathophysiology of Medical Parasites: Mechanisms of Disease and Immune Evasion

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Abstract

Medical parasites are diverse organisms that can cause significant morbidity and mortality worldwide. Understanding the pathophysiology of these parasites is crucial for developing effective treatment and prevention strategies. This review explores the mechanisms through which medical parasites induce disease and evade host immune responses. Key parasitic pathogens, including protozoa, helminths, and ectoparasites, employ various strategies to establish infection and promote survival within the host. Mechanisms of tissue invasion, such as the secretion of proteolytic enzymes and the alteration of host cell signaling pathways, are critical for establishing parasitic niches. Additionally, many parasites possess sophisticated immune evasion tactics, such as antigenic variation, secretion of immunomodulatory molecules, and the ability to mimic host antigens. These adaptations allow parasites to persist in hostile environments and evade detection by the host immune system. The interplay between the parasite's pathogenic mechanisms and the host's immune response is complex, leading to a range of clinical manifestations, from mild to severe disease. Understanding these interactions not only sheds light on the biology of these organisms but also highlights potential targets for therapeutic intervention. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the pathophysiological processes underlying parasitic infections and their implications for public health.

Keywords: *Parasite-Host Interaction, Immune Evasion Strategies, Pathogenic Mechanisms, Chronic Infection, Host Immunity Modulation, Parasite Virulence Factors.*

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Introduction to Medical Parasites

Medical parasites are one of the oldest and most important classes of pathogens impacting human health worldwide. More than three billion people in the world are chronically infected with at least one species of parasite, and in the world's most vulnerable and low-resource ecological communities, the majority of the population is likely to carry parasites that affect health and well-being. Parasitic disease impacts human communities significantly, causing chronic debility and either reduced lifespan or an increased burden of chronic disability. Many of these infections also cause a range of acute and chronic encephalopathies, including cognitive impairments in children, which is likely to lead to long-term impacts on local health and health-seeking behaviors. At the most severe end of the spectrum, the major disease-determining aspects of the infection, and as these diseases move from non-consensual to consensual relationships with their hosts, a greater understanding of how the host immune system fails to effectively and consistently protect against these microorganisms is indicated. Medical parasites are broadly defined as

eukaryotic organisms, belonging to several kingdoms, including protozoa, helminths, arthropods, and fungi, that are adapted to live at the expense of their vertebrate hosts in a parasitic relationship. Parasites can be classified into a number of operational categories, including site specificity, hosts, life stages, or form or outcome of the interaction. While these categories have the advantage of offering specific labels for naming parasites, it is important to appreciate that in practice, parasitic relationships are unstable—significantly or transiently—and likely to encompass a range of stages and ecological roles for a given parasite species. Life cycles include mono- or polycyclic microorganisms, depending on whether they have one or more associated single hosts or host taxa, respectively (Bhanot, 2021; Schuster, 2008). Lotic protozoa have very small and consistent taxonomic levels other than the family level. Parasites can be found inside host cells, or the open space inside all organs and tissues can be universally colonized by parasites. An extended atlas of the presence and relative abundance of species of parasites in different host tissues and organs is of particular interest when also linked to disease outcome (Brehm, & Lüder, 2009).

Definition and Classification

A parasite is an organism that lives on or in a host organism, usually to the latter's disadvantage. For the convenience of scientific study, parasites are classified according to varying criteria. The most common criteria are:

- Anatomy, i.e., whether they are multicellular worms or unicellular. The former can be further classified according to the gross structure of their bodies as nematodes and platyhelminthes (Rodriguez, Suo, & Liu, 2024).
- Protozoa and helminths can be further classified using evolutionary perspectives (Christaki, 2020).

Medical parasites are broadly classified into four groups based on various criteria:

- 1. Protozoa:** contain a single cell and, unlike other eukaryotic microbes, they can possess a number of highly specialized organelles that are analogous to the organs of multicellular organisms. They are also characterized by their mobility. The pathogenic diversity of these unicellular parasites can range from mild symptoms to death (Christaki, 2020).
- 2. Helminths (worms):** multicellular organisms with numerous cells. Helminths can be classified into nematodes, cestodes, and trematodes.
- 3. Ectoparasites:** blood-sucking arthropods and insects are an abundant group of parasites. They include hematophagous Diptera, Hemiptera, Hymenoptera, and Siphonaptera. Ectoparasites are the vectors for a significant number of known infectious disease agents (Christaki, 2020; Mahmud, Lim, & Amir, 2017).

Global Impact and Epidemiology

Medical parasites burden public health around the world. The annual global costs of some parasitic diseases are of major concern and lead to a large amount of resources needed to combat them annually. Hookworm and schistosomiasis each help to drain more than 3 billion USD from the economies of sub-Saharan Africa, South-East Asia, and the Americas annually. Most parasitic diseases have prevalence rates of greater than 50% in sub-Saharan Africa, East Africa, and Oceania, while the incidence in other tropical areas can have prevalence ranging from 21% to 35%. Most vulnerable are children aged 5-14 years and pregnant women, who have limited access to healthcare delivery (Fitzpatrick, 2013). The high prevalence of some of these diseases in different subpopulations is usually related to an infected person's socioeconomic and environmental conditions. Some of the key links to disease spread and transmission are unimproved drinking water and sanitation, as well as unsafe water, sanitation, and hygiene services in the schools where parasitic infections are most easily acquired via open defecation. Additionally, populations in urban centers typically have higher rates of infection than those in rural areas, where the

economic and social status of many, especially the urban poor, means that they are susceptible to several neglected tropical diseases. Not to be forgotten are the soldiers who are posted to disease-endemic areas around the world (Maurice, et al., 2020). Also vulnerable are these types of people, as well as those who are exposed to some of the factors mentioned above. Because these diseases are considered by some to be of minor public health importance versus the big three, they are usually added as an afterthought to the bottom of the global health agenda, and as a result, resources to eliminate them are typically limited. These gaps need to be addressed in order to help ensure that the most comprehensive control packages are being considered (Fitzpatrick, 2013; Maurice, et al., 2020).

Host-Parasite Interactions

Infections are of crucial medical importance, threatening humans and animals with various parasites, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, and eukaryotic microorganisms. The primary concern about these diverse organisms includes: first, their method of penetration into the host, avoidance of host defense mechanisms, and evasion of immune-mediated killing; and second, the method for maintaining and increasing their transmission between hosts. Consistent with microscopic pathogens, parasites exist on a spectrum of multicellular organisms, varying from large macroparasites to small microparasites. There are a variety of extraordinary mechanisms that parasites might use to gain access to and exist within the host. At its center, host-parasite interactions are a competition for energy and nutrition. However, these interactions also have a number of severe ramifications for parasites that are related to this basic concept. On one hand, infection and dissemination of parasites to other hosts are made easier in exchange for the high replication rates in a host that may dramatically alter host ecology in a manner that makes the parasites more likely to be transmitted (Wolinska, & King, 2009). As a result, many parasites evolved to cleave the immune defenses of their hosts by enduring or even using the immune response to acquire entry to and exist within the host and utilize more unusual ecosystems. More parasites have adapted to several distinct tissues within the host and represent a range of possible adaptations to life therein. The growth of the immune response to infecting parasites is of interest due to the consistent variations regarding the unique biology of parasites. Infections are regulated under the influence of a variety of factors working together (Dheilly, 2014; Dzik, 2006).

Mechanisms of Invasion and Colonization

Probably every animal and plant has at least one species that parasitizes it, making medical parasites but a tiny subset. Nevertheless, the invasion of a host and successful colonization of tissues are major phases of the life cycle and disease of medically important parasites. A more thorough understanding of the many mechanisms by which this comes about will guide new research efforts into preventive and therapeutic strategies (Dzik, 2006). The most important mechanisms by which parasites invade tissue and cells are reviewed here for protozoans, helminths, and arthropods. When considering all these various means that parasites have evolved to invade their hosts, a question of considerable interest is whether the host has caps on these mechanisms, and, if so, how effective the caps are. Clearly, once a parasite has invaded its host, that host is very often parasitized for life unless it dies or therapy intervenes. Most, if not all, invaders are recognized by host defenses irrespective of number, and using diverse means of invasion provides important avenues for immune evasion of the host defenses that recognize the original invader. A good example of this, also involving manipulation of host tissues, is seen in the helminths. It follows that the likelihood of severe disease following an infection may either increase or decrease (Mustafa, Hamad, & Mohsein, 2024; Goedknecht, et al., 2016).

Immune Response to Parasitic Infections

A substantial immune response is developed in response to a parasitic infection. In general, the host utilizes a variety of strategies aimed at keeping the parasite under control and preventing severe disease.

Strategies used include the action of eosinophils and mast cells that release cationic proteins, the activity of complement, and the release of defensins. During primary parasitic infection, antigen-specific effector cells from both the innate and acquired immune responses are required to bring the infections under control. Immune cells that are important in combating parasite infections include eosinophils, polymorphonuclear neutrophils, macrophages, and natural killer cells in the innate immune response, and B cells and T cells in the adaptive response (Brandonisio, & Spinelli, 2002). The eosinophil is an immune cell well known for its role in the immune response triggered after infection with helminths. Eosinophils produce a number of toxic mediators that can damage and immobilize the parasites and contribute to parasite expulsion. Conversely, parasites have adopted strategies to avoid being attacked or killed by eosinophils. Parasites have developed mechanisms to influence the host's immune response, leading to a more passive infection by avoiding or dampening the induction of certain immune cells and cytokines. Infections will become chronic if the suppressive strategies of the parasites are not surpassed to allow efficient responses to be initiated by the host on time. After invasion by some parasites, physical obstacles such as the blood-brain barrier or the endoplasmic reticulum are used as a shield for the parasites, and therefore CD4⁺ T cells and macrophages find it difficult to reach and attack the infection site effectively (Montaner, et al., 2014). Variability in immune responses elicited by different hosts has also been reported depending on the species of host. The role of the memory responses by the immune system will result in an even more effective elimination of the parasites by the host if exposed to the parasites after infection, even if healed with chemotherapy. However, the intensity and the type of the immune responses elicited during a parasitic infection are important. The immune response at the site of infection must be appropriate, i.e., not too low or too high. Regulation of the immune responses by certain parasites will, however, not only lead to suboptimal attempts at controlling the infection by the host, but it is also associated with the development of chronic infection by the parasite and the generation of immunopathology as an infection outcome. The severity of pathology in wild infected hosts is, however, very dose-dependent, with low-intensity infection usually leading to more expression of pathology when compared to high-intensity exposures (Aguirre-García, et al., 2020).

Pathogenesis of Parasitic Diseases

Tissue invasion by parasitic organisms is a substantial contributor to the mechanisms of disease behind parasitic infections. By providing a sanctuary in an internal organ, parasites may escape the attack by phagocytic cells of the many blood and lymphatic elements responsible for dealing with external infections. Protection from the host immune response is often carried out by the expression of a molecular structure known as a coat of many sugars (Hamad, Mustafa, & Mohsein, 2024). This coat is composed of oligosaccharide side chains conjugated to glycoproteins or glycolipids that are periodically altered to minimize the impact of the immune reaction. Animals exposed to a repetitive series of infections form antibodies against various parasite coat sugars, and this may result in an array of circulating immune complexes. The complexes may injure the host either through classic immunopathology resembling that seen in systemic immune complex disease or through the combined toxic action of the parasites and their encased antibodies or complement components. Thus, tissues can be injured by a variety of host reactions (Wynn, & Kwiatkowski, 2001). The final common pathway of immune damage is a complement-mediated membrane attack that disrupts helminths, mosquitoes, and target cells. Long-term temperatures inflamed and oxygen-deprived can result in serious health outcomes. Also, microbes or parasites can cause tissue alteration through the secretion of cytokines, defecation of waste products, and larval migration. Long-term outcomes of tissue alteration can be due to oxidative stress, dysregulation of growth factors, and signaling pathways. The clinical picture resulting from such host responses is often quite protean, with patients presenting at different times and over varying intervals of illness with any combination of symptoms and immunodiagnostic responses (Rashidi, et al., 2021).

Tissue Damage and Organ Dysfunction

Enteric and tissue-dwelling parasitic protozoans and helminths can directly damage host tissues during their migration, and they feed and reproduce inside the host. A number of lytic enzymes are synthesized and released by the parasites that can disrupt the integrity of the gastrointestinal mucosal epithelium, for chemoattraction and penetration of tissues, and disable the host cellular signaling pathways that mediate a variety of protective responses to worm and arthropod vectors. The immune-mediated damage is mediated through tissue inflammatory responses to large parasite burdens and the chronic presence of parasites, and the extensive deposition of proteolytic and fibrogenic mediators and oxidative stress cascades that these responses trigger (Silva Pereira, et al., 2019).

Because many parasites establish infections within the GI tract but are not primarily destroyed by the action of enteric enzymes, living adult worms can accumulate in GI tissues and blood vessels. For the small-diameter venules of the upper legs and abdomen, tissue-dwelling worms can then occlude the outflow of blood, obstruct the flow of lymph, or progressively dilate lymphatic vessels. These events cause what is known as 'lymphadenopathy' and 'lipo-lymphedema,' and can be manifested by gross enlargements of the feet, legs, genitalia, or uterine tube resulting from the abnormal increases of tissue fluids and collection of immune cells and debris. Infections common in a variety of organs can also lead to chronic conditions and contribute to severe morbidity (Daher, et al., 2022). Even after effective killing of enteric parasites, damages induced by either the parasites themselves or by associated enteropathies that become irreversible may still cause long-term complications. Timely dying of parasites has a great impact in alleviating organ dysfunction. Thus, it is important to elucidate the entire process of pathophysiological mechanisms of parasite infection and transmission (Bienvenu, Gonzalez-Rey, & Picot, 2010; Kirchhoff, et al., 2004).

Clinical Manifestations

Allow the learners to describe the varied clinical manifestations of parasitic infections on the basis of the host and organ system involved, different populations at risk, at risk in different life stages, and age groups. Use the etiology for diagnosis. Overlap different disease processes in the differential diagnosis. Emphasize the need for early recognition, the initial assessment, and the importance of a complete parasitic infection description in the diagnosis. Infections with parasites are caused by eukaryotic organisms and lead to an enormous spectrum and diversity of clinical symptoms. Clinical manifestations range from asymptomatic carriage to acute or long-lasting chronic disease and debilitating sequelae. Many infections with parasites are caused by worms and invade various organs and tissues in the human host. The liver, the lungs, the skin, the blood, the heart, the central nervous system, the gastrointestinal tract, and the genitourinary tract, as well as the lymphatic system, are often involved. Parasitic infections occur particularly among the world's poor, and some 300 million people each year become ill with one or more of the most common parasitic diseases. Prevalence rates vary, but almost everyone has been colonized. Monitoring parasitic infections is challenging due to inconsistent clinical presentations (Nunes, et al., 2017). Malaria and schistosomiasis are examples of the numerous causes of fever and eosinophilia in travelers or immigrants. Toxoplasmosis is responsible for life-threatening central nervous system disease, and toxocariasis and cysticercosis are responsible for eosinophilia in children and adults in urban and rural settings. Clinical experience in the management of patients with parasitic infections is crucial, particularly in the use of novel, expensive antiparasitic drugs and dealing with the absence of indications by health regulatory authorities. The risk of toxoplasmosis depends on the population, and malnutrition and immune suppression in migrants due to various reasons can act as facilitators. Natural immunity develops in approximately half of the population of a highly endemic area over a 20-year period. Uterine infection in pregnancy leads to more severe toxoplasmosis in offspring. Synergism of sexual promiscuity in the developing world and HIV has made congenital and pediatric toxoplasmosis highly prevalent in several countries. Other established clinical manifestations include gastrointestinal and cardiac disease with eosinophilia. Pulmonary toxocariasis and ocular toxoplasmosis are unusual. The management of the

infections includes the alleviation of symptoms in conjunction with etiological remedies. A review of the clinical aspects of some of the common species of parasitic, helminthic, and protozoal infections is presented (Peng, 2002; Raether, & Hänel, 2003).

Immune Evasion Strategies

Immune evasion. Within the hostile environment of an animal host, parasites must efficiently evade damage by the immune system or face elimination. Such evasion strategies are likely to be as old as parasites themselves and are an absolute requirement for the survival of a pathogenic parasite. The two principal evasion strategies, in essence, buy time or avoid host killing and encompass three primary mechanisms. Trans-equilibrium is achieved by cytoadhesion of circulating parasites and the sequestration of tissue trophozoites and schizonts in organ beds essential for parasite survival. Antigenic variation, where parasites maintain low-level growth by expressing one of a series of variant surface antigens in order to escape immune destruction. Modulation of some immune effectors to downregulate host resistance and dampen protective anti-parasite immunity is primarily associated with chronic pathology which, while gradually disabling the host, still allows parasite propagation. This evasion is achieved by avoiding lysis and hiding within existing tissue beds and the array of molecules and proteins that the parasite employs to modulate host cell processes in order to avoid host defense (Hambrook, & Hanington, 2021). The result of these strategies is chronic infection and a long-term relationship. Parasite evasion of host physiological responses and host defenses are complex finely tuned systems of potential host and parasite responses which are likely the outcome of frequent coevolution molded by biological processes, including those of reproduction but guided by the ultimate twin imperatives of host life and parasite survival. These observations hold true for all medically important parasites and their hosts. Evolutionary pressures and tremendous biological success also result in a high degree of biological diversity among parasites. Immune evasion is obviously central to parasite success and understanding these issues can help shape vaccine and drug policy as well as design (Oladiran, & Belosevic, 2012; Gomes, et al., 2016).

Antigenic Variation

A second strategy that has been described in pathogens is antigenic variation, in which pathogens continually change surface antigens, thereby evading attack by the host immune response. Many of these antigens are contained in large gene families. The best-documented examples of antigenic variation in human parasites are PfEMP1, the variable major protein of *B. hermsii*, and the variant surface glycoprotein of *Trypanosoma brucei*. In the cases of *B. hermsii* and *T. brucei*, they switch between genes that encode variable antigens so that at any given time, their surface antigens are not under attack. Even though the existence of LFERs in subtelomeric regions of several *Plasmodium* species divergent from *P. falciparum* suggests that widespread antigenic variation mechanisms may exist in the genus, antigenically variant antigens in these species have as yet not been identified. It is generally assumed that the biological significance of antigenic variation is to maintain chronic infection so that new infections in other uninfected hosts can continue. However, it is also clear that, with ongoing antigenic variation, at some stage, the host immune system will be able to recognize all the variants (Stephens, 2020). Therefore, this needs a balance between the variation capacity and the capacity of effective effector cell mechanisms to limit the production of the constantly changing immunodominant antigens. Several studies have shown that in high parasitemia, VSG- or PfEMP1-specific immune responses may comprise up to 50% of all antibodies in the sera of infected individuals. The continual modification of the major antibody target of the host immune response complicates experimental work as a plethora of variants have to be studied. Similarly, vaccination development will be a difficult task. Moreover, in many cases, just knowing the sequences of variants is not enough; further assays of their effects on infected people are needed.

Contacts with those currently or recently infected are likely to point the way to the most effective antigens and assays for these evaluations (Gross, Hsu, & Deitsch, 2021).

Immunomodulation

Immunomodulation manipulating the host immune system is also a powerful strategy that pathogens use to establish and maintain infection. The immune response is complex and involves multiple components that act in concert with one another to destroy invading pathogens. By inhibiting or diverting these components, parasites can work to decrease the effect of immune attack, lower their chances of detection, or generally make the environment inhospitable to immune cells. Moreover, infections with elevated inflammation can cause increased tissue damage and can be harder to resolve. As the hero of the immune system is also a double-edged sword, able to attack the invading parasites but also able to create chronic diseases if not managed properly. Parasites use a number of methods to disrupt the human immune response. Several parasites are known to directly inhibit the action of immune cells. One parasite secretes a protein that encapsulates and effectively 'switches off' dendritic cells, decreasing their presentation of antigen and, hence, assisting parasite evasion. Alternatively, a number of parasites interfere directly with T and B cells to inhibit the production of effector cells. For example, a molecule expressed by another parasite can elicit the production of T and B cells that express specific receptors and are able to produce the anti-inflammatory regulatory cytokine IL-10. This increased activity among parasites to manipulate and suppress the immune response has been pinpointed as one of the key factors contributing to helminth infection being a major cause of impairment in human populations. Such manipulation of the immune response provides the opportunity to develop a regulatory environment that increases the chances of tissue survival and permits continued survival and reproduction of the parasite within host tissues. Immunomodulation can set the tone of the developing disease (Santos, et al., 2021). High levels of pro-inflammatory responses are associated with stronger immunopathology, while some parasites cause immunosuppression and thus jeopardize the contribution of the immune response. Controlling and resolving infection is related to a strong attack of effector immunity, generally dependent on Th1 over Th2 immunity, and the capacity to produce anti-inflammatory IL-10 suppressor cells may also be important in harmonizing pathogenic inflammation. Understanding the evolution of these processes is significant in the design of new therapies that will stimulate a protective response in those who are unable. Moreover, the strategies used by parasites to modulate innate and adaptive immunity may determine disease outcomes or susceptibility to different forms of parasites within the population. When the types of molecules are detected at the site of infection, they may also create the conditions for a protective response, such as adult worm resistance or a form of protective immunity that is likely to reduce the severity of symptoms following re-infection. Differences between parasites therefore contribute to the clinical manifestations of disease and could also account for the heterogeneity observed in vaccine studies for parasites with projected numbers of cases. In combination, these strategies highlight the potential for immune responses to each stage of the antigenic life cycle and should be an important focus for future research in host adaptive responses (Mustafa, Hamad, & Mohsein, 2024).

Diagnosis and Treatment

Until quite recently, the diagnosis of parasitism naturally occurred in both developing and developed countries, as the spectrum of infections tended to differ. Samples would be processed in a special room, where the technician would examine them under the microscope and report their findings to the attending physician. A long history of veterinary pathology reports informs us that this is the most unsatisfactory of the methods of examining and the largest possible number of specimens in the shortest possible time. A large number of diagnostic tools have been developed in a routine care setting to diagnose infection with these medically important parasites. These can be broadly divided into 'traditional' and 'modern' methods, with the latter largely focused on detection through immunological methods.

Both traditional and modern diagnostics have advantages and disadvantages in terms of their sensitivity, specificity, and utility in different clinical situations (Santos, et al., 2020). Perhaps their most notable disadvantage is having a lower sensitivity than direct microscopy, which is especially problematic for sub-microscopic infections and has led to cross-sectional studies in high-prevalence areas suggesting that microscopy can significantly underestimate the prevalence of some anti-malarial immunity. Microscopy is a high-throughput method yielding results in a reasonable timeframe, but its sensitivity is its biggest downfall on its own and is affected by the technical and practical skills of the microscopist. By using a combination of microscopy and an immunological test, an infection can be detected with a higher degree of sensitivity and a lower likelihood of a false negative result. The current study used a number of techniques to demonstrate the performance of these approaches in a symptomatic cohort in southwestern Uganda. Indeed, we have taken several steps to show a highly symptomatic participant, perhaps the most likely to carry multiparous infections, which may be the case in an area of intensive immunity to anti-malarial drugs. Drug infection suppression therapy also enables microscopically detectable infection. At present, no human vaccines are effective against any of the most common parasitic infections. Even in the infected individuals most rapidly susceptible to the clinical severity of the disease and most likely to be the focus of a vaccine approach, the approach is prophylactic for prophylaxis. In the treatment of parasitic diseases, the decision-making and the choice of chemotherapeutic agents are based on several factors. The patient's poverty affects the likelihood of compliance and the possibility of side effects from expensive drugs, duration of hospitalization, knowledge of the drugs, the perceived safety of the drug, previous experiences, efficacy-based, locally frequent drugs, or grade affixed to the disciplined community-directed therapy, individual and aggregated population pharmacokinetics, community sentiment for drugs as well as guidelines, availability, pharmaceutical prices, cost, frequency of drug delivery, genetic diversity and variability in parasite species, sex, and level of endemicity. The structural salient pathogens are essentially the same, with probable differences in the mechanism of drug resistance resulting in changes in the IC50 or drug-derived KAR. The drug choice in adults and children for schistosomiasis, and benznidazole for American Trypanosomiasis, is relatively well documented. However, in other clinical groups, at present, the decision of the extension is primarily made on the basis of experience and inconvenience (Dantas-Torres, et al., 2020; Lightowers, et al., 2021).

Diagnostic Methods

Conventional laboratory diagnoses of parasites that cause human disease have traditionally employed microscopy of relevant clinical materials, culture techniques, serology, or combinations of these approaches. Microscopy is highly specific and, for some infections, highly sensitive, and can facilitate direct visualization and quantification of a range of organisms. However, it is labor-intensive, potentially requires a degree of expertise, and is often limited by the need for fresh and correctly collected clinical materials, which may in themselves exhibit low levels of the infecting organism. Serology is highly sensitive and semiquantitative, and thus useful in monitoring infection load over time or in response to antiparasitic treatment but may test positive for an extended period after successful treatment, vaccine-induced immunity, or prior disease (Santos, et al., 2020). Culture techniques may be used to identify certain parasites that cannot be easily identified directly because they are not in a readily observable life cycle stage in clinical specimens and may also facilitate susceptibility testing. However, they are, again, labor-intensive. Development of diagnostic tools based on PCR and antigen detection assays in recent years has been pivotal for some diseases. Consequently, where resources are available, heavily labor-intensive, time-consuming, and relatively insensitive tests that rely on fresh diagnostic samples are being replaced by much more robust and highly sensitive, largely blood-based molecular and serological assays. The choice of an appropriate diagnostic strategy or combination of methods is very much dependent on the infection profile or likely infecting agents in a specific patient population; chronicity and typical symptoms of the disease in an affected population; the availability of specimens from the site of infection;

and the cost, infrastructure, and expertise available to already developing countries. Efforts into the development of new and improved diagnostics must be ongoing to address these issues. Epidemiological studies in low-income settings are further complicated by the variable or non-specific, long-term sequelae of many infections and the difficulty in obtaining rapid, reliable diagnostic results for them. Advances in the diagnostic area are not only critical for parasites but hold the key to improving care across the infectious disease spectrum (Verocai, Chaudhry, & Lejeune, 2020; Slater, et al, 2022).

Pharmacological Interventions

In recent years, the development of parasiticidal drugs has gained momentum, in part due to the advent of automated high-throughput screening technologies that allow for the rapid identification of compounds that kill parasites at low micro- or nanomolar concentrations *in vitro*. Most of the currently available anti-parasitic medications can be divided into several classes, each designed to inhibit the growth, replication, or survival of the largest possible range of parasites of a single type. The microbicidal mechanisms of compounds are diverse, with primary targets often being proteins, nucleic acids, carbohydrates, and cell walls, among a few. Others exert their effects via enzymatic sabotage, interference with physiological processes, and functional mimicry of essential biomolecules, mostly being cell infiltrators or modulators. Although these drugs are clearly effective in improving short-term patient outcomes, drawbacks include the emergence and spread of drug resistance, non-target activity of the drugs, and in some cases, limited access to health services. Currently, the prominent use of antiprotozoals may influence the outcome of schistosomiasis, warranting careful reintroduction of the effects and perceived risks of these drugs (Rao, et al., 2023; Fontinha, Moules, & Prudêncio, 2020).

Drug combinations may increase the diversity of pathways and functional modules that have to be targeted simultaneously in order to affect pathogen cells negatively, reducing the risk of drug resistance. The kinds of combinations considered include the use of more than one drug class or more than one drug within the same class and are likely to meet the goal of improved patient care. This hypothesis is supported by the efficacies seen in recent clinical trials of anti-malarial agents. With this background in mind, we will explore several newer drugs under development, discussing their mechanism of action as well as their use in reducing the impact on the host. Ongoing attempts are being made to conduct commercial trials to further define the best clinical practices in severely affected groups. Given that important issues of patient interactions and regimens are raised, it is not premature to consider these now (Fontinha, Moules, & Prudêncio, 2020; Wilkinson, et al., 2023).

Prevention and Control

Prevention and control of parasitic diseases consist of both population-based strategies aimed at reducing transmission, as well as individual-based strategies targeting both uncomplicated and severe infections. Public health strategies focus on reducing the transmission of parasites, either by increasing the apparent resistance against the infection or by increasing the ineffectiveness to reduce further transmission. In communities endemic for parasitic diseases, disease prevention may be performed through community education and awareness, dissemination of policies that support intersectoral action and international cooperation. At a personal level, prevention may also be provided through the use of vaccines, vector control strategies, treatment, and chemoprophylaxis. Possibly, the combination of more comprehensive and integrated strategies can involve different actions and tools developed at three different stages of the parasite lifecycle inside humans, vectors, and the environment (Ziarati, et al., 2022). Despite many efforts and important goals achieved, vaccines remain at an early stage. Implementing vaccination and immunization strategies also involves focusing on the most appropriate categories of people to vaccinate at the national scale and prioritizing those people at the community level. As a result, vaccination prevention may achieve little effectiveness in the near future, including in different low-middle income

countries. Integrated vector management involves environmental management and other measures to suppress, prevent, and limit the spread of vector populations. Integrated vector management provides valuable preparedness for the introduction of new tools and can help to prolong the efficacy of existing insecticides and mitigate the potential impact of the development of insecticide resistance. In comparison to the large investment in new drug treatment development and procurement, far less attention and research funding have been allocated to the development of high-quality, safe, and effective second-generation vaccines and combination tools against parasitic diseases. On the other hand, despite the use of control strategies in the fight against the main neglected tropical diseases, their related prevention measures depend mainly on the parasitic stage and pathophysiologic mechanism of disease. Moreover, the fully effective, safe, and equitable utilization will also depend on the context and geographical area, driven by the economic scenarios in different countries that are of particular interest in low-middle income countries, where these diseases have a significant negative impact in terms of direct medical costs and productivity loss. Further studies are highly necessary to explore cost-effective and user-friendly interventions or combined measures (Negara, et al., 2022; Ehrenberg, et al., 2020).

Vaccines and Immunization Strategies

6. Vaccines and Immunization Strategies. The employment of vaccination or immunization strategies for the prevention of parasitic diseases has long been recognized, yet relatively few have been implemented. Successful vaccines against relatively few parasites, such as *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Eimeria tenella*, and *Plasmodium chabaudi*, have been developed, tested, and commercialized (Solana, et al., 2022). Active vaccine development programs currently focus on human leishmaniasis, human African trypanosomiasis, and lymphatic filariasis. In human leishmaniasis, parasites from the *Leishmania donovani* species complex are the focus of extensive clinical trials, with numerous live conditionally attenuated parasites and virally vectored vaccines in clinical trials. While subunit leishmanial vaccines are still in development and/or preclinical, data to date indicate that a recombinant two-protein vaccine has potential for multiple forms of human leishmaniasis (Sander, et al., 2020; Tang, et al., 2022).

Vaccines and Immunization Strategies:

Three factors are important for the reduction of morbidity and mortality arising from parasitic infections:

- Safe, effective antiparasitic drugs for treating those already infected, which must be distributed to local health centers and taken properly as prescribed.
- Antiparasitic drugs effective for prophylaxis, strategically distributed to prevention programs monitored to minimize the development of resistance (Sander, et al., 2020).
- Medications capable of clearing latent, asymptomatic, and acute infections. However, these approaches mainly address parasite susceptibility. Vaccine-induced herd immunity is only achieved with broad vaccine coverage and compliance allowing a reduction in parasite transmission rates to levels ensuring that the resultant effective R_0 is <1 , leading to a long-lasting reduction in new disease incidence (Yasmin, et al., 2022; Chu, & Quan, 2021).

Vector Control

From the previous subsection, it is evident that vector transmission greatly influences the transmission of parasites. Effective vector control can reduce the risk of new infections, decrease the transmission of parasites, and interrupt the transmission of parasites. A vector control strategy should be planned simultaneously with other highly effective control strategies to reduce morbidities and mortalities. Controlling malaria transmission via environmental management measures and biological control methods is recommended. Controlling indoor transmission through the use of long-lasting insecticidal nets and indoor residual spraying is also recommended. The control of diseases driven by parasites transmitted through a variety of vectors should contemplate integrated vector management activities,

targeting the most effective way to control the different species of vectors to reduce disease transmission. Controlling the vectors of parasites is a necessary step for parasite control because some parasites, like leishmaniasis, do not typically have good drugs for clinical treatment. Additionally, the eradication of human diseases transmitted by vectors relies heavily on controlling vector populations. Vectors transmit parasites by taking blood (and therefore the parasites) from an infected vertebrate (the host), after which the parasites develop within the vector. The vector then transmits the infective form of the parasites to another susceptible vertebrate (the host). A variable portion of susceptible vertebrates will exhibit morbidity and be subsequently highly infectious to vectors. When one component in the development cycle of the vector, such as the density, feeding habits, or susceptibility, is interrupted, disease transmission is also terminated (Wilson, et al, 2020; Manikandan, et al., 2023).

Emerging Challenges and Research Directions

The emergence and spread of drug-resistant parasites has limited the number of available treatment options for many parasitic diseases. This carries a substantial cost in terms of morbidity, mortality, and economic impact that arise as a consequence of treatment failure. At present, there are few new drugs in the research and development pipeline, and it is clear that the loss of effective treatments has the potential to cause major public health problems. As such, the need to explore non-traditional approaches to drug development that consider the nature of the tripartite interactions associated with cell infection is clear. In response, integrated research programs and structural biology initiatives to develop these therapies are being supported by accelerating bioinformatics and systems biology research (Chala, & Hamde, 2021). This is driving substituted strategies to anticipate and constrain the consequences of poor therapeutic choices in the future. The ever-changing nature of host-pathogen-parasite interactions should ultimately drive targeted drug discovery to reduce the impact of resistance. Pathogen and parasitic diseases, as well as vectors carrying them, are very sensitive to climate. In recent years, climate change has led to the further development of many parasitic diseases. The process of climate change affects the parasitic life cycle, changes the distribution and quantity of parasites, further increases the infectious pressure on the target population, and may lead to various parasitic diseases. As such, some studies have pointed out that a few parasitic diseases of medical importance may have the potential to spread further. At the same time, both additional interdisciplinary teams specializing in the evaluation of emerging health threats and targeted studies of individual diseases could help to predict the future impact of these emerging parasitic threats on health. A full understanding of these threats to human health should be supported by the development of new anti-parasitic drugs that are potentially more effective against a broader spectrum of parasites (Mansoldo, et al., 2020; Karunarathna, et al., 2024).

Drug Resistance

Anti-parasitic drugs are widely used in regions where parasitic infections are endemic. Increases in drug resistance prevalence have been reported for most pathogenic parasites, and the mechanisms underlying drug resistance are being intensively studied. Parasites can develop drug resistance through a range of mechanisms, many of which have been adapted from cellular and molecular biology or from clinical cancer research and can also be found in bacteria. The development of resistance against the most commonly used compounds has been investigated over the years. No new class of anti-plasmodium drugs has been introduced in the last two decades. Artemisinins are now hampered by drug resistance in Southeast Asia and may meet the same fate as former antimalarials. Chloroquine resistance is now universal and sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine resistance is characterized by a quintuple mutation, despite efforts to eliminate it. The problem of resistance is also being encountered in helminths, though it seems to be less important in protozoa. Drug resistance in onchocerciasis has also emerged and spread. The issue of drug resistance documents the multiple levels of determinants, from underlying socio-economic conditions to the necessity to develop new tools to overcome this problem. Moreover, drug resistance

may translate into a higher disease burden. Although liver transplants are beneficial, post-transplant infection can lead to a far more severe form of leishmaniasis known as immune reconstitution inflammatory syndrome during the recovery of T-cell functions. Public health policies such as insecticide-treated nets to fight against malaria and onchocerciasis are important, but they should not lead to neglecting current research against drug resistance. Surveillance and monitoring of the drug resistance situation seem mandatory in order to set up a clear strategy. Other drugs that have passed phase I trials, including P27 and prophylactic treatments, should be pushed into new field trials with drugs alone or in combination. Alternatively, support could be given to vaccines, such as those against malaria or schistosomes, to help reduce the pressure. A lesson can be taken from other microorganisms, such as tuberculosis or HIV, for which therapy is based on a multiple-drug combination; for example, a whole treatment to reduce the extent of transmission (Shibeshi, Kifle, & Atnafie, 2020; Peng, et al., 2021).

Climate Change and Parasite Distribution

Opportunistic or "emerging" parasites dynamically interact with changes in the global environment. There is a consensus among infectious disease ecologists that biogeographic disease patterns will shift because of climate, which will, in turn, cause latitudinal changes in patterns of transmission. Examples of parasites that have bounced back through the Anthropocene include orbiviruses, dengue, chikungunya, avian influenza, *Yersinia pestis*, *Enterocytozoon bieneusi*, West Nile virus, borreliosis, echinococcosis, and schistosomiasis. Vectors, such as sandflies, ticks, and mosquitoes, should find altered irrigation schemes, warmer overwintering, uninterrupted lifespans, and thus expanded habitat zones due to this warming trend. Not all climatic change has been reported to favor the spread of infectious diseases. For instance, hookworm larval maturation was reduced in a warmer winter while ionoregulation could handle the accompanying increase in precipitation, which ultimately reduces transmission. Overhead, however, lies the fact that frequent climatic anomalies coincide with disease outbreaks when transmission can be re-established (Byers, 2021). Higher environmental temperatures result in an increase in the multiplication of parasites per generation, increased progression in the life cycle, and higher infection rates among cold-blooded intermediate hosts. Season length affects the prevalence and number of infective stages shed, but if extended, it can exhaust the outbred immune system brought forth by the prolonged re-infection mechanisms. A wet period can raise the number of eggs and infective stages per gram of feces, flood snails in water courses, increase the number of well-watered areas, and thus require grazing at increasingly irrigated pastures. The end result is that a person can contact more sporocyst stages per snail shed. The number of sporocysts in various snail species increased due to the excessively heavy rainfall in Venezuela in 1983. Impacts on animal bodies also reduce immune responses. If two vector-competent mosquito species are used concomitantly and the host switches from one vector to another for amplification, then the survival of the first vector between normal vector replacement may be crucial (Byers, 2020; Tidman, Abela-Ridder, & Ruiz de Castañeda, 2021).

Conclusion

Medical parasites employ sophisticated mechanisms to establish infection, evade the host immune system, and sustain their survival. These mechanisms include antigenic variation, suppression of host immune responses, and manipulation of cellular pathways to avoid detection. Understanding the pathophysiology of these parasites provides critical insights into their disease-causing processes and the chronic conditions they may induce. Additionally, unraveling their immune evasion strategies highlights potential targets for therapeutic intervention and vaccine development. Future research should focus on exploring innovative approaches to mitigate the impact of these parasites, ultimately reducing their global burden and improving health outcomes in affected populations.

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References

- Aguirre-García, M. M., et al. (2020). TLR-mediated host immune response to parasitic infectious diseases. In *Toll-like Receptors*.
- Akhoundi, M., et al. (2016). A historical overview of the classification, evolution, and dispersion of *Leishmania* parasites and sandflies. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 10(3), e0004349.
- Anderson, R. M., May, R. M., & Gupta, S. (1989). Non-linear phenomena in host–parasite interactions. *Parasitology*, 99(S1), S59–S79.
- Bhanot, P. (2021). Introduction to parasites. In *Practical Handbook of Microbiology* (pp. 665–682). CRC Press.
- Bienvenu, A. L., Gonzalez-Rey, E., & Picot, S. (2010). Apoptosis induced by parasitic diseases. *Parasites & Vectors*, 3, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1756-3305-3-1>
- Brandonisio, O., & Spinelli, R. (2002). Immune response to parasitic infections—An introduction. *Current Drug Targets - Immune, Endocrine & Metabolic Disorders*, 2(3), 193–199.
- Brehm, K., & Lüder, C. G. K. (2009). Introduction: Parasites. In *Host-Pathogen Interactions: Methods and Protocols* (pp. 239–243).
- Byers, J. E. (2020). Effects of climate change on parasites and disease in estuarine and nearshore environments. *PLOS Biology*, 18(11), e3000743. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000743>
- Byers, J. E. (2021). Marine parasites and disease in the era of global climate change. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 13(1), 397–420. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010419-010725>
- Chala, B., & Hamde, F. (2021). Emerging and re-emerging vector-borne infectious diseases and the challenges for control: A review. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 715759. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.715759>
- Christaki, E. (2020). Classification of parasitic diseases. In *The Surgical Management of Parasitic Diseases* (pp. 23–45).
- Chu, K.-B., & Quan, F.-S. (2021). Advances in *Toxoplasma gondii* vaccines: Current strategies and challenges for vaccine development. *Vaccines*, 9(5), 413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9050413>
- Daher, E. D. F., et al. (2022). Kidney complications of parasitic diseases. *Nature Reviews Nephrology*, 18(6), 396–406. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41581-022-00548-3>
- Dantas-Torres, F., et al. (2020). TroCCAP recommendations for the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of parasitic infections in dogs and cats in the tropics. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 283, 109167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2020.109167>
- Dheilly, N. M. (2014). Holobiont–holobiont interactions: Redefining host–parasite interactions. *PLoS Pathogens*, 10(7), e1004093.

- Dzik, J. (2006). Molecules released by helminth parasites involved in host colonization. *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, 53(1), 33–64.
- Ehrenberg, J. P., et al. (2020). Strategies supporting the prevention and control of neglected tropical diseases during and beyond the COVID-19 pandemic. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, 9(1), 135–141. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-020-00766-9>
- Fitzpatrick, J. L. (2013). Global food security: The impact of veterinary parasites and parasitologists. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 195(3–4), 233–248.
- Fontinha, D., Moules, I., & Prudêncio, M. (2020). Repurposing drugs to fight hepatic malaria parasites. *Molecules*, 25(15), 3409. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25153409>
- Goedknegt, M. A., et al. (2016). Parasites and marine invasions: Ecological and evolutionary perspectives. *Journal of Sea Research*, 113, 11–27.
- Gomes, P. S., et al. (2016). Immune escape strategies of malaria parasites. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 7, 1617. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.01617>
- Gross, M. R., Hsu, R., & Deitsch, K. W. (2021). Evolution of transcriptional control of antigenic variation and virulence in human and ape malaria parasites. *BMC Ecology and Evolution*, 21, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12862-021-01755-3>
- Hamad, A. A., Mustafa, H. M., & Mohsein, O. A. (2024). Detection of the levels of immune cytokines (IL-4, IL-5, TNF- α) in school-age and preschoolers with an *Ascaris lumbricoides* infection. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 48, 782–787. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12639-024-01715-w>
- Hambrook, J. R., & Hanington, P. C. (2021). Immune evasion strategies of schistosomes. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 11, 624178. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2020.624178>
- Karunaratna, I., et al. (2024). Mebendazole: A pillar in the fight against helminthic infections and emerging challenges.
- Kirchhoff, L. V., et al. (2004). Parasitic diseases of the heart. *Frontiers in Bioscience*, 9(1–3), 706–723.
- Lightowers, M. W., et al. (2021). Advances in the treatment, diagnosis, control, and scientific understanding of taeniid cestode parasite infections over the past 50 years. *International Journal for Parasitology*, 51(13–14), 1167–1192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpara.2021.10.002>
- Mahmud, R., Lim, Y. A. L., & Amir, A. (2017). Medical parasitology. Cham, Switzerland: Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68795-7>
- Manikandan, S., et al. (2023). A review on vector-borne disease transmission: Current strategies of mosquito vector control. *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 85(3), 503–513. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-8172.2022.00271.7>
- Mansoldo, F. R. P., et al. (2020). Chagas disease: Perspectives on the past and present and challenges in drug discovery. *Molecules*, 25(22), 5483. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25225483>
- Maurice, A. P., et al. (2020). Epidemiology of parasitic diseases. In *The Surgical Management of Parasitic Diseases* (pp. 3–21).
- Montaner, S., et al. (2014). The role of extracellular vesicles in modulating the host immune response during parasitic infections. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 5, 433.
- Mustafa, H. M., Hamad, A. A., & Mohsein, O. A. (2024). *Entamoeba histolytica* and *Giardia lamblia* predominance in Iraq's southern governorates. *International Journal of Environmental Health Engineering*, 13(1), 10.

- Mustafa, H. M., Hamad, A. A., & Mohsein, O. A. (2024). Investigating specific calprotectin and immunological markers associated with intestinal infections caused by *Entamoeba histolytica*. *Iranian Journal of Veterinary Medicine*, 18(4).
- Negara, K. S. P., et al. (2022). One health strategy in prevention and control of parasitic zoonosis globally and Indonesia—from theory to practice: A mini-review. *Bali Medical Journal*, 11(3), 1537–1542. <https://doi.org/10.15562/bmj.v11i3.3430>
- Nunes, M. C. P., et al. (2017). Cardiac manifestations of parasitic diseases. *Heart*, 103(9), 651–658. <https://doi.org/10.1136/heartjnl-2016-310928>
- Oladiran, A., & Belosevic, M. (2012). Immune evasion strategies of trypanosomes: A review. *Journal of Parasitology*, 98(2), 284–292. <https://doi.org/10.1645/GE-2840.1>
- Peng, M., et al. (2021). Endoplasmic reticulum stress: A target for drug design and drug resistance in parasitosis. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 12, 670874. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.670874>
- Peng, S. L. (2002). Rheumatic manifestations of parasitic diseases. *Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism*, 31(4), 228–245. <https://doi.org/10.1053/sarh.2002.31754>
- Raether, W., & Hänel, H. (2003). Epidemiology, clinical manifestations and diagnosis of zoonotic cestode infections: An update. *Parasitology Research*, 91(5), 412–438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-003-0980-2>
- Rao, S. P. S., et al. (2023). Drug discovery for parasitic diseases: Powered by technology, enabled by pharmacology, informed by clinical science. *Trends in Parasitology*, 39(4), 260–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2022.12.001>
- Rashidi, S., et al. (2021). The host mTOR pathway and parasitic diseases pathogenesis. *Parasitology Research*, 120, 1151–1166. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-07047-1>
- Rodriguez, A., Suo, X., & Liu, D. (2024). Classification of medically important parasites. In *Molecular Medical Microbiology* (pp. 2907–2919). Academic Press.
- Sander, V. A., et al. (2020). Use of veterinary vaccines for livestock as a strategy to control foodborne parasitic diseases. *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, 10, 288. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2020.00288>
- Santos, H. M., et al. (2020). Common bacterial, viral, and parasitic diseases in pigeons (*Columba livia*): A review of diagnostic and treatment strategies. *Veterinary Microbiology*, 247, 108779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2020.108779>
- Schuster, F. L. (2008). Introduction to parasites. In *Practical Handbook of Microbiology* (pp. 751–786). CRC Press.
- Shibeshi, M. A., Kifle, Z. D., & Atnafie, S. A. (2020). Antimalarial drug resistance and novel targets for antimalarial drug discovery. *Infection and Drug Resistance*, 13, 4047–4060. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S279644>
- Silva Pereira, S., et al. (2019). Tissue tropism in parasitic diseases. *Open Biology*, 9(5), 190036. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsob.190036>
- Slater, L., et al. (2022). Current methods for the detection of *Plasmodium* parasite species infecting humans. *Current Research in Parasitology & Vector-Borne Diseases*, 2, 100075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpvbd.2022.100075>
- Solana, J. C., et al. (2022). Live attenuated vaccines: A favorable strategy to provide long-term immunity against protozoan diseases. *Trends in Parasitology*, 38(4), 316–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2021.12.009>

- Stephens, R. S. (2020). Antigenic variation of *Chlamydia trachomatis*. In *Intracellular Parasitism* (pp. 51–62). CRC Press.
- Tang, B., et al. (2022). Vaccines as a strategy to control trichinellosis. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 13, 857786. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.857786>
- Tidman, R., Abela-Ridder, B., & Ruiz de Castañeda, R. (2021). The impact of climate change on neglected tropical diseases: A systematic review. *Transactions of The Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 115(2), 147–168. <https://doi.org/10.1093/trstmh/traa192>
- Verocai, G. G., Chaudhry, U. N., & Lejeune, M. (2020). Diagnostic methods for detecting internal parasites of livestock. *Veterinary Clinics of North America: Food Animal Practice*, 36(1), 125–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cvfa.2019.10.006>
- Wilkinson, V., et al. (2023). Time to consider pharmacological interventions against infectious disease in wildlife. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 60(2), 229–236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14291>
- Wilson, A. L., et al. (2020). The importance of vector control for the control and elimination of vector-borne diseases. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 14(1), e0007831. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0007831>
- Wolinska, J., & King, K. C. (2009). Environment can alter selection in host–parasite interactions. *Trends in Parasitology*, 25(5), 236–244.
- Wynn, T. A., & Kwiatkowski, D. (2001). Pathology and pathogenesis of parasitic disease. In *Immunology of Infectious Diseases* (pp. 293–305).
- Yasmin, H., et al. (2022). Host–pathogen interaction in leishmaniasis: Immune response and vaccination strategies. *Immuno*, 2(1), 218–254. <https://doi.org/10.3390/immuno2010016>
- Ziarati, M., et al. (2022). Zoonotic diseases of fish and their prevention and control. *Veterinary Quarterly*, 42(1), 95–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01652176.2021.2024426>